

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF VARIOUS ENDOSCOPIC FINDINGS IN
DYSPEPTIC PATIENTS****Dr. Riaz Hussain Awan^{1*}, Dr. Seema Nayab², Dr. Ameet Jesrani³, Dr. Khadim Hussain Awan⁴, Dr. Faqir Muhammad Awan⁵ and ⁶Dr. Ali Raza Shaikh**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Gastroenterology, LUMHS Jamshoro²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, LUMHS Jamshoro³Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation (SIUT) Karachi⁴Resident, Department of Urology Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore⁵Resident Cardiology Shaikh Zaid Hospital Lahore⁶Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad / Jamshoro**Abstract:****Objective:** To evaluate the frequency of various endoscopic findings in dyspeptic population.**Patients and Methods:** The Cross sectional study was placed in the department of Gastroenterology, Liaquat National Hospital from 17 Jan 2011 to 16 July 2011. The informed consent was taken and all the dyspeptic patients underwent for endoscopy while the endoscopic findings were explored and saved on proforma to analyze them in SPSS version 13.**Results:** Total one hundred ninety five dyspeptic populations were explored with mean age \pm SD was 41.52 ± 15.04 years with 17.89 ± 8.51 months duration of symptoms. Ninety eight (50.3%) were males and ninety seven (49.7%) were female. The common findings traced were pangastritis, hiatus hernia, antral gastritis, esophagitis, esophageal candidiasis and duodenal polyp were observed in 84 (43.1%), 54 (27.7%), 37(19%), 15 (7.69%), 4 (2.1%) and 1 (0.512%) patients respectively.**Conclusion:** The common endoscopic findings traced were pangastritis, hiatus hernia, antral gastritis, esophagitis, esophageal candidiasis and duodenal polyp were observed in dyspeptic patients respectively.**Key Words:** Dyspepsia, Pangastritis, Esophagitis, Hiatus hernia.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Riaz Hussain Awan,**
Department of Gastroenterology,
LUMHS Jamshoro

QR code

Please cite this article in press Riaz Hussain Awan *et al.*, *Frequency of Various Endoscopic Findings in Dyspeptic Patients.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Dyspepsia is highly prevalent disorder and reported 25% of population each year but the affected patients usually ignored either self or by health care provider [1-3]. For proper diagnosis a careful history and physical examination, supplemented by selected tests, including upper gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy usually lead to a correct diagnosis [4]. Endoscopy usually evaluates the underlying organic lesion and etiology for dyspepsia such as gastroduodenal ulcer disease, erosive esophagitis or gastric cancer [5]. The symptoms commonly overlap, making diagnosis difficult [6]. Majority of dyspeptic population have endoscopic and histopathological evidence of gastritis and *H. pylori* infection and the disorder is responsible for substantial health burden and social absence [7,8]. The prevalence of dyspepsia in Pakistan is not known but it is thought to be high, despite the fact that only 20-25% seeks medical advice [9]. Since dyspepsia affects large numbers of people across a broad spectrum of symptoms, it is not practical to perform endoscopy in all patients [10]. The evaluation and management of dyspepsia constitutes a significant clinical and economic burden [11]. The rationale of this study was to determine the frequency of different endoscopic findings in dyspeptic population as the prevalence of GI malignant disorders is higher and this population usually ignored and managed conservatively without intervention. There are several less invasive and non expensive tools are available for *H. pylori* detection and the maneuvers can lead to decrease the economical burden and population can be treated on non invasive parameters successfully.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The cross sectional six months (17 Jan 2011 to 16 July 2011) study was conducted at Liaquat National Hospital. Prevalence of pangastritis in dyspeptic patient 15%; based on these findings, estimated sample size on 5% bound of error and 95 % Confidence Interval with a prevalence of 15% comes out to be 195 patients

The inclusion criteria were:

1. Dyspeptic patients.
2. Either gender.
3. Age 15-45 years.

The exclusion criteria were:

1. Patient with complaint of coffee ground vomiting, Malena, Weight loss, Hematemesis.
2. Patients with anemia.

3. Diagnosed patients with gastrointestinal or other malignancies.
4. Diagnosed case of chronic liver disease.
5. Age >45 years
6. Family history of Gastrointestinal Malignancy.

Dyspepsia: Presence of at least two of the following symptoms of more than a one month duration will be considered as dyspepsia

1. Epigastric pain or burning sensation
2. Upper abdominal fullness
3. Nausea

Endoscopic Findings:

Hiatus Hernia
Esophagitis
Esophageal Candidiasis
Pangastritis
Antral Gastritis
Duodenal Polyp

Informed consent was taken and all patients under went endoscopy, that was done by consultant and senior residents (who have experience of more than 3 years); endoscopic findings were saved on proforma and analysis was done through SPSS-13. All continuous response variables like age and duration of symptoms were presented in mean and standard deviation with 95% confidence interval. Frequency & percentage and mean \pm SD were computed while the stratification was done to observe the outcomes.

RESULTS:

Total one hundred ninety five dyspeptic populations were studied with mean age \pm SD 41.52 \pm 15.04 years and 17.89 \pm 8.51 months duration of symptoms. Ninety eight (50.3%) were males and ninety seven (49.7%) were female. Regarding co-morbid diabetic mellitus was detected in 65(33.3%) cases, hypertension 14 (7.18%) and IHD was observed in 2(1.02%) cases. Multiple co-morbid were also observed in patients which were presented in single co-morbid.

Endoscopic finding according to age, gender and duration of symptoms are also presented in table 3 to 5 respectively. Rate of gastritis, esophagitis and pangastritis was above 50% in below 40 years of age patients while rate of hiatus hernia was 57.4% in above 40 years of age. Rate of gastritis and hiatus hernia was above 50% in male patients while esophagitis and pangastritis was above 50% in female patients. Similarly endoscopic finding with respect to duration of symptoms. The results are presented in Figure 1-4 and Table 1-2.

FIGURE 1: AGE DISTRIBUTION OF THE PATIENTS n=195

FIGURE 2: GENDER DISTRIBUTION n=195

FIGURE 3:DURATION OF SYMPTOMS n=195

FIGURE 4:ENDOSCOPIC FINDING n=195

TABLE 1:ENDOSCOPIC FINDING WITH RESPECT TO AGE GROUPS n=195

ENDOSCOPIC FINDING	Age_Group2		Total
	<= 40 n=104	> 40 n=91	
Antral Gastritis	21(56.8%)	16(43.2%)	37
Hiatus Hernia	23(42.6%)	31(57.4%)	54
Esophagitis	11(73.3%)	4(26.7%)	15
Pangastritis	49(58.3%)	35(41.7%)	84
Duodenal Polyp	0(0%)	1(100%)	1
Esophageal Candidiasis	0(0%)	4(100%)	4

TABLE 2:ENDOSCOPIC FINDING WITH RESPECT TO GENDER n=195

ENDOSCOPIC FINDING	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Antral Gastritis	16(43.2%)	21(56.8%)	37
Hiatus Hernia	25(46.3%)	29(53.7%)	54
Esophagitis	8(53.3%)	7(46.7%)	15
Pangastritis	46(54.8%)	38(45.2%)	84
Duodenal Polyp	1(100%)	0(0%)	1
Esophageal Candidiasis	2(50%)	2(50%)	4

DISCUSSION:

Gastrointestinal disturbances which include esophagitis, antral gastritis, pangastritis, duodenitis, gastroduodenal ulcers and other inflammatory conditions are a worldwide problem among all age groups. Several causative factors have been identified contributing to the development of these complications [12]. These include age, gender, hyperacidity, smoking habit, alcohol consumption, and use of nonsteroid anti-inflammatory drugs. Beside these factors, now there is strong evidence that bacterial agent *H. pylori* can cause gastritis, gastric ulcer, duodenal ulcer and non-ulcer dyspepsia [13]. The history and physical examination supplemented with appropriate laboratory, radiographic, and endoscopic investigation leads to the correct cause of dyspepsia in most cases. Routine blood counts and blood chemistry determinations are commonly obtained. They can be requested selectively depending upon patient features such as age, symptom duration, and other factors. These tests help to identify patients with alarm symptoms (e.g. anemia) who require endoscopy or other diagnostic testing [14]. Total one hundred ninety five dyspeptic patients were included with mean age \pm SD was 41.52 \pm 15.04 years. This is almost similar to study Ahmed J, et al in which 446 patients were enrolled with a mean age was 38.86 years [15]. Mean age of my patients was younger than mentioned by Kulich KR, et al¹⁶ 47.5 years and this difference in age could be due to difference in life span in western countries as comparative to our population.

In present series, ninety eight (50.3%) were males and ninety seven (49.7%) were female. Diabetic mellitus was observed in 65(33.3%) cases, hypertension 14 (7.18%) and IHD was observed in 2(1.02%) patients. Multiple co-morbid were also observed in patients which were presented in single co-morbid.

In present study, pangastritis was observed in 84(43.1%) patients, where as in international studies the incidence of pangastritis (77.3%) with mostly mild active inflammation (60.6%) and was found most commonly in the age group 31-60 years [17], whereas incidence of pangastritis is reported as 112 (100%) in former study [18]. The hiatus hernia was seen 54(27.7%), whereas in international study the incidence of hiatus hernia 160(36%) cases by Ladabaum U, et al [18] whereas in another international study the incidence of hiatus hernia 24

(47%) cases by Lorenz R, et al [18]. The antral gastritis was detected in 37(19%) cases, whereas in international study the incidence of Antral gastritis 20% by Tytgat GNJ [19] whereas in local study the incidence of Antral gastritis 76.2% by Din Z [20]. The esophagitis was observed in 15(7.69%) cases, whereas in international study the incidence of esophagitis 95(21%) cases by Ladabaum U, et al [18], whereas in local study the incidence of esophagitis 64.3% by Din Z [20]. The esophageal candidiasis 4(2.1%), whereas in international study the incidence of the esophageal thrush was scattered in 57(97%) and diffuse in only two patient by Al Mofleh IA, et al [21]. Whereas in local study the incidence of the esophageal candidiasis 69(47.9%) by Zafar H, et al^{3,22} The duodenal polyp was observed in one case, whereas in international study the incidence of duodenal polyp 6(0.17%) cases by Strak SK [23], whereas in local study the incidence of duodenal polyp 4(28.6%) cases. [24]. Endoscopic finding with respect to age, gender and duration of symptoms are also presented in table 3 to 5 respectively. Rate of antral gastritis, esophagitis and pangastritis was above 50% in below 40 years of age patients while rate of hiatus hernia was 57.4% in above 40 years of age. Rate of antral gastritis and hiatus hernia was above 50% in male patients while esophagitis and pangastritis were above 50% in female patients. Therefore, the dyspeptic subjects can be managed with H₂- blockers, PPIs or pro-kinetics although the response usually varies. The data is limited that dyspeptic individuals can be managed thru psychiatric medication. In summary, the important step in managing dyspepsia is to exclude organic disorder and management strategies based on existence of *H. pylori* and duration and severity of symptoms.

CONCLUSION:

The dyspepsia is a chronic common but complicated disorder found in general population while in present study the common endoscopic findings traced were pangastritis, hiatus hernia, antral gastritis, esophagitis, esophageal candidiasis and duodenal polyp were observed in dyspeptic patients respectively.

REFERENCES:

1. Talley N J., Vakil N and Practice Parameter committee of the American College of Gastroenterology - Guide line for Management

- of Dyspepsia *Am J Gastroenterol* 2005; Oct 100:2324–37.
2. Dent J, Brun J, Fendrick AM, Fennerty MB, Janssens J, Kahrilas PJ, et al. An evidence-based appraisal of reflux-disease management - the Genval workshop report. *Gut* 1999;44(suppl 2):S1-S16
 3. Marwaha A, Ford A, Lim A, Moayyedi P - McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario The Worldwide Prevalence of Dyspepsia Systemic Review and Meta Analysis - Search CDDW 2009;126.
 4. Talley NJ, Sidney FP Non Ulcer Dyspepsia: Potential Causes and Pathophysiology 1988;108:865-79.
 5. Parkman HP. Non-Ulcer Dyspepsia Current treatment option in Gastroenterology - 1998;1:15-9.
 6. Small PK, Loudon MA, Waldron B, Smith D, Campbell FC. Importance of reflux symptoms in functional dyspepsia. *Gut* 1995;36:189-192
 7. Hamama-tul-Bushra K, Muhammad U, Muhammad K, Masood K, Zahid M; et al - PakMedinet Endoscopic and Histopathological Evaluation of 306 Dyspeptic Patients - 2003;17:4-7.
 8. Agreus L, Talley NJ. Dyspepsia: current Understanding and Management Annual Review of Medicine.1998;49:475-93.
 9. Ashraf HM, Shahzad A, Saeed F, Mehtab M, Asad S Is It Worthwhile to Treat H-Pylori in all Dyspeptic Patients 2005; 2:1-8.
 10. Jones RH, Lydeard SE, Hobbs FD, Kenkre JE, Williams EI, Jones SJ, et al. Dyspepsia in England and Scotland. *Gut*. 1990;31(4):401-5.
 11. Uri L, Viam D Rate and yield of repeat upper endoscopy in patients with Dyspepsia *World J Gastroenterol* 2010;16:2520.
 12. Wong WM, Wong BCY, Hung WK, Yee YK, Yip AWC, Szeto ML, et al. Double blind, randomised, placebo controlled study of four weeks of lansoprazole for the treatment of functional dyspepsia in Chinese patients. *Gut* 2002;51:502-6.
 13. Peura DA, Kovacs TO, Metz D, Gudmundson JL, Pilmer BL. Low-dose lansoprazole: effective for non-ulcer dyspepsia (NUD). *Gastroenterology* 2000;118:A439 (abstract).
 14. Moayyedi P, Soo S, Deeks J, Forman D, Mason J, Innes M, et al. Systematic review and economic evaluation of *Helicobacter pylori* eradication treatment for non-ulcer dyspepsia. *Br Med J* 2000;321:659-64.
 15. Ahmed J, Haider SI, Choudhri AN. Dyspepsia in a rural cohort. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2004 Feb;14(2):91-3
 16. Kulich KR, Malfertheiner P, Madisch A, Labenz J, Bayerdorffer E, Miehke S, et al. Psychometric validation of the German translation of the Gastrointestinal Symptom Rating Scale (GSR) and Quality of Life in Reflux and Dyspepsia (QOLRAD) questionnaire in patients with reflux disease. *Health Qual Life Outcomes*. 2003; 1: 62.
 17. Atisook K, Kachinthorn U, Luengrojanakul P, Tanwandee T, Pakdirat P, Puapairoj A. Histology of gastritis and *Helicobacter pylori* infection in Thailand: a nationwide study of 3776 cases. *Helicobacter*. 2003 Apr;8(2):132-41
 18. Ladabaum U, Dinh V. Rate and yield of repeat upper endoscopy in patients with dyspepsia. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2010 May 28;16(20):2520-5.
 18. Lorenz R, Jorysz G, Clasen M. The globus syndrome: value of flexible endoscopy of the upper gastrointestinal tract. 1993;107(6):535-7.
 19. Tytgat GNJ. Role of endoscopy and biopsy in the work up of dyspepsia. *Gut* 2002; 50:13-16
 20. Din Z. Endoscopic Findings in Dyspepsia a Prospective Study of 200 cases. *JPMI*.2003;17(2):235-39.
 21. Al Mofleh IA1, Al Mofarreh MA. Esophageal candidiasis among a dyspeptic population. *Saudi J Gastroenterol*. 1999 May;5(2):61-5.
 22. Zafar H, Rizwan SF, Hayyat A Balouch, Mohmand A Q K. Frequency of oral candidal carriage in type II diabetic patients and association with acid peptic disease. *Isra Med J*.2011;3(2):48-51
 23. Strak SK. Upper Gastro Intestinal Endoscopy Findings In Patients with Dyspeptic symptoms in Basrah. *IJGE*.2002;1(3): 45-8
 24. Inayatullah M, Anjum AH, Nazish Z, Dr. Naqvi AB, Akhtar MS. Dyspepsia and upper gastrointestinal endoscopy. *Professional Med J Mar* 2008;15(1): 143-147.